

DEVELOPING A STRATEGIC FRAMEWORK FOR SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP AS A DRIVER OF GRASSROOTS DEVELOPMENT: A MULTI-STATE ANALYSIS OF SOUTHEAST NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study examined the developing a strategic framework for social entrepreneurship as a driver of grassroots development: a multi-state analysis of southeast Nigeria. The objectives of the study were to examine the effect of social capital dimensions on poverty alleviation in South-East Nigeria; determine the effect of social innovation dimensions on poverty alleviation in South-East Nigeria; assess the effect of social value creation dimensions on poverty alleviation in South-East Nigeria. The study was motivated by the persistence of grassroots poverty in the region despite strong entrepreneurial traditions, community networks, and self-help structures. The study adopted a survey design and covered the five states of south-east Nigeria, namely Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo. a sample size of 422 respondents was determined using the Cochran formula and selected through a multi-stage sampling technique. Primary data were collected through a structured questionnaire. Face and content validity were established, while reliability was confirmed using Cronbach's alpha. Data were analysed using regression analysis. The findings revealed that social capital dimensions had significant effects on poverty alleviation ($t=1.544, p=0.123$); social innovation dimensions had significant effects on poverty alleviation, ($t=2.861, p=0.004$); social value creation dimensions had significant effects on poverty alleviation, ($t=2.223, p=0.027$); the study concluded that the strategic framework developed from the findings provides a practical guide for strengthening social entrepreneurship as a tool for poverty alleviation in south-east Nigeria. The study recommends that Nigeria should strengthen their institutional and external linkages with government agencies, donor bodies, financial institutions, and development partners; managers and coordinators of social ventures should give greater attention to process innovation and institutional innovation; social entrepreneurship programmes should be based on proper

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identification of real community needs.

1.1 Background to the Study

Development at the grassroots level remains a major policy and research concern in Nigeria because poverty, vulnerability, and social exclusion still affect a large share of the population. The 2022 Nigeria Multidimensional Poverty Index shows that 63% of Nigerians are multidimensionally poor, while poverty is more severe in rural areas, where 72% of the population is poor compared with 42% in urban areas. Recent World Bank projections also indicate that poverty in Nigeria may rise further, reaching 53.4% in 2026, unless reforms improve livelihoods and expand productive work. These realities show that conventional state-led interventions alone have not fully solved local welfare problems and that alternative community-based development mechanisms deserve deeper scholarly attention (National Bureau of Statistics [NBS], 2022; World Bank, 2026).

The case of South-East Nigeria makes this issue more compelling. The zone is widely associated with enterprise, local initiative, and dense community networks, yet recent labour market evidence shows that important pockets of

deprivation remain across the states. In the 2023 Annual Nigerian Labour Force Survey, unemployment rates in the South-East states varied sharply, with Abia at 18.7%, Imo at 10.9%, Enugu at 5.9%, Anambra at 4.8%, and Ebonyi at 3.7%. The same report shows that the youth not in education employment and training (NEET) rate was 38.1% in Abia and 17.9% in Anambra. These figures suggest that enterprise-rich settings can still experience serious livelihood deficits, weak labour absorption, and unequal access to opportunity. This strengthens the argument for a multi-state inquiry into development drivers at the grassroots level rather than a single-state study (NBS, 2024a).

Within this context, social entrepreneurship has emerged as a relevant development pathway. Current global literature shows that social entrepreneurship is increasingly viewed as a means of addressing social problems through innovative, mission-driven, and locally embedded ventures. The World Intellectual Property Organization noted in the *Global Innovation Index 2024* that definitions of social

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entrepreneurship vary across legal and policy systems, but the field is now strongly linked with innovation, societal impact, and transformative problem-solving. Recent scholarship also describes social entrepreneurship as especially important in environments marked by inequality, informality, and institutional gaps. In the Nigerian context, Arejiogbe et al. (2023) argue that social entrepreneurship can support poverty alleviation through job creation, access to services, and broader social improvement (Ndubuisi, 2021). This means that social entrepreneurship is not only an economic activity. It is also a social intervention mechanism with potential grassroots consequences (Arejiogbe et al., 2023; Raman, 2025; World Intellectual Property Organization [WIPO], 2024).

Entrepreneurship is the ability and willingness to initiate a private enterprise for profit making. Entrepreneurship is mainly driven by business success. Business success is primarily achieved through profit making. Generally, it is profit making and business success that motivates entrepreneurs to start a business. But there is a type of Entrepreneurship that is not primarily driven by profit making and that is Social Entrepreneurship (Orajaka, 2021).

Thus, social enterprises are formally established, autonomous, value-based enterprises, established to achieve social, environmental and cultural objectives, and are set up, to serve unmet needs in the society. The impact on society, rather than wealth creation becomes the primary value created. In recent years social entrepreneurship, a sub-discipline within the field of entrepreneurship, has gained increasing attention from entrepreneurship scholars. Social entrepreneurship involves the recognition, evaluation, and exploitation of

opportunities that result in social value — the basic and long-standing needs of society-as opposed to personal or shareholder wealth. Social value has little to do with profits but instead involves the fulfillment of basic and long-standing needs such as providing food, water, shelter, education, and medical services to those members of society who are in need (Mutarubukwa and Mazana, 2017).

The term "social entrepreneurship" describes the process of locating, assessing, and seizing opportunities that have societal value. An entrepreneur's capacity to discern whether there is a supply or demand for a service or product that adds value is reflected in their opportunities awareness and identification. Social entrepreneurs are well aware of the requirements of society and use innovative organization to meet those needs (Fuso et al., 2024). Health and medical services, information communication and computer technology (ICT), trade and commerce, manufacturing, agriculture, education, financial services, fashion design, culture, recycling, the green economy, social media, and skit creation are just a few of the industries that are impacted by these social entrepreneurship endeavors.

Additionally, social entrepreneurship differs from corporate social responsibility (CSR). For instance, a company that supplies mosquito nets to a community affected by malaria for free is not the same as a company that establishes a mosquito net manufacturing facility in the area after determining that the area has a potential market. Again, there are differences between creating a sachet and bottled water company in the same location and supplying guinea worm disease-endemic communities with water from a borehole. Although social entrepreneurship may not seem like a well-thought-out idea at first, it will become more apparent as time

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passes thanks to intuition and generosity. Along with encouraging volunteerism, social entrepreneurship lowers unemployment and idleness, which in turn lowers social vices, particularly among youth (Islam, 2022; Schätzlein et al., 2023).

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to examine the effect of social entrepreneurship on poverty alleviation in South-East Nigeria and develop a strategic framework, with employment creation as a moderating variable. The specific objectives are to: examine the effect of social capital dimensions on poverty alleviation in South-East Nigeria.

1. Determine the effect of social innovation dimensions on poverty alleviation in South-East Nigeria.

2. Assess the effect of social value creation dimensions on poverty alleviation in South-East Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Social Entrepreneurship

Social entrepreneurship refers to the use of entrepreneurial ideas, structures, and actions to solve social problems and create social value. It differs from conventional entrepreneurship because its central goal is not private profit alone. Its central goal is social improvement through innovative and sustainable solutions (Manafa, Okeke & Atueyi 2022). In this sense, social entrepreneurship combines mission, innovation, and measurable social outcomes. Current literature also shows that the concept is now linked strongly with innovation systems, local problem-solving, and impact-oriented ventures.

In the Nigerian context, social entrepreneurship has become more relevant because poverty, unemployment, weak public service delivery,

and local welfare gaps remain serious development problems. Nigerian evidence shows that social entrepreneurship can support poverty reduction by creating jobs, expanding access to services, and improving social and economic conditions. Arejiogbe et al. (2023), using data from social entrepreneurs in Nigeria and PLS-SEM analysis, found that social innovation, social value, and social impact significantly improved poverty alleviation. In the same direction, Abang (2024) found in Abuja that community social entrepreneurship served as a complementary approach to government poverty reduction efforts. These studies show that social entrepreneurship in Nigeria is increasingly viewed as a practical development mechanism rather than only a theoretical idea.

2.1.2 Poverty Alleviation

Poverty alleviation refers to the reduction of deprivation through improved income, better access to basic needs, enhanced opportunities, and improved living conditions. It is broader than temporary relief. It involves a sustained reduction in the conditions that make households and communities poor. In Nigeria, this concept remains very important because poverty is still widespread. The Nigeria Multidimensional Poverty Index reported that 63% of Nigerians were multidimensionally poor in 2022, while recent World Bank projections indicate that poverty remains a serious national concern. This shows why poverty alleviation remains an appropriate dependent variable for a study on grassroots development.

Local studies in Nigeria also support the use of poverty alleviation as a measurable development outcome. Abang (2024) treated poverty reduction as the outcome of community social entrepreneurship in Abuja. Shiaki et al. (2024) examined poverty reduction as the

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outcome of social capital in Benue State. Sofoluwe et al. (2024) also measured rural poverty reduction through household consumption indicators in Nigeria. These studies show that poverty alleviation can be operationalized through welfare improvement, reduced deprivation, and better livelihood conditions. This makes it suitable as the single dependent variable in the present study.

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Social Capital Theory

Social Capital Theory explains how networks, trust, norms, and relationships create access to support, cooperation, and resources. The theory is commonly associated with Bourdieu (1986), Coleman (1988), and Putnam (1993). Bourdieu viewed social capital as actual and potential resources connected to durable networks of relationships. Coleman saw it as a productive social structure that facilitates action. Putnam emphasized trust, reciprocity, and civic engagement as foundations of collective welfare. The theory is relevant to social entrepreneurship because social ventures often operate in environments where formal institutions are weak or limited. In such settings, relationships and networks become important sources of information, trust, labour, legitimacy, and support. This is especially true in grassroots communities where collective action depends heavily on social ties.

The present study applies Social Capital Theory through bonding social capital, bridging social capital, and linking social capital. Bonding social capital explains close ties within families, kinship groups, and local communities. Bridging social capital explains connections across different groups and communities. Linking social capital explains vertical ties with government agencies, donors, financial institutions, and other power structures. These

forms of capital are important for understanding how social entrepreneurship mobilizes people and resources for poverty alleviation in South-East Nigeria.

The theory is appropriate for the study because the South-East Nigerian context is strongly shaped by kinship networks, community associations, informal support systems, and collective self-help traditions. These structures may support the emergence, survival, and expansion of social entrepreneurial activities.

A limitation of Social Capital Theory is that strong internal ties may sometimes lead to exclusion, closure, or overdependence on familiar networks. However, this limitation is reduced in the present study by disaggregating social capital into bonding, bridging, and linking forms. This makes the theory more useful and balanced for analysis.

2.3 Empirical Review

Shiaki et al. (2024) examined the impact of social capital on poverty reduction in Benue State, Nigeria. The study used primary survey data and logit regression. Poverty reduction was the dependent variable, while cooperative participation, social media involvement, rural group membership, social club membership, and political party membership served as the explanatory variables. The study found that cooperative participation, social media involvement, rural group membership, and social club membership reduced poverty. The study is relevant because it provided recent Nigerian evidence on the poverty-reducing effect of social capital. However, it focused only on social capital and did not integrate other dimensions of social entrepreneurship.

Sofoluwe et al. (2024) assessed the effect of social capital on rural poverty reduction in Oyo State, Nigeria. The study adopted primary household data and analysed the data using the

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Foster–Greer–Thorbecke index and Tobit regression. Rural poverty reduction was the dependent variable, while social capital dimensions were used as the independent variable. The findings showed that social capital improved food consumption expenditure and reduced poverty. The study confirmed that social ties and networks can improve welfare among rural households. However, the scope was limited to rural farming households.

Okunmadewa et al. (2007) analysed the effects of social capital on rural household welfare in Nigeria using household survey data and econometric regression. Household welfare was the dependent variable, while social capital was the independent variable. The study found that social capital improved household welfare and reduced poverty. The study is important because it showed that social capital contributes positively to welfare outcomes in rural Nigeria. However, it focused on welfare and did not examine social entrepreneurship.

Adepoju et al. (2012) examined social capital and household welfare in Nigeria under endogeneity conditions. The study used primary household data and applied the control function approach. Household welfare was the dependent variable, while social capital was the independent variable. The result showed that social capital remained welfare-enhancing even after correcting for endogeneity. This strengthened the empirical credibility of the welfare effect of social capital. However, the study did not address poverty alleviation directly as a broader social entrepreneurship outcome.

Yusuf (2008) investigated the effect of social capital on household welfare in Kwara State, Nigeria. The study used survey data and regression analysis. Household welfare was the dependent variable, while social capital was the

explanatory variable. The finding showed that social capital significantly improved welfare. This supports the view that social relationships and participation can improve household living conditions. However, the single-state focus limits broader generalisation.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study adopted the survey research design. The design was also appropriate because the study involved the collection of data from respondents at one point in time through a structured questionnaire.

3.2 Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of founders, managers, coordinators, and principal officers of social entrepreneurial ventures and community-based development organizations in South-East Nigeria. These included social enterprises, community development associations, cooperatives, women empowerment groups, youth development groups, non-governmental organizations, faith-based development initiatives, and other grassroots ventures that combined entrepreneurial activities with social objectives. Since the study focused on social entrepreneurship as a driver of poverty alleviation, respondents were drawn from organizations and initiatives that were directly involved in local welfare improvement, livelihood creation, poverty reduction, community support, or other socially oriented entrepreneurial activities.

Where an updated and complete sampling frame was available from state ministries, cooperative registries, SMEDAN records, NGOs, and relevant associations, the accessible population was determined from those records before field administration.

3.3 Sample Size Determination

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Because the study **covered** multiple states and the exact number of eligible social entrepreneurial actors **was not** fully known at the planning stage, the sample size **was determined** using the **Cochran formula** for large or unknown populations:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 pq}{e^2}$$

Where:

- n = sample size
- Z = standard normal deviation at 95% confidence level = 1.96
- p = estimated proportion of the population with the required characteristic = 0.50
- q = 1 - p = 0.50
- e = margin of error = 0.05

Thus,

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2(0.50)(0.50)}{(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{3.8416 \times 0.25}{0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{0.9604 \times 0.25}{0.0025} = 384.16$$

The minimum sample size for the study is therefore **384 respondents**.

To take care of non-response, poorly completed questionnaires, and field losses, 10% **was added**:

$$10\% \text{ of } 384 = 38.4$$

$$384 + 38 = 422$$

Therefore, the final sample size for the study was **422 respondents**.

For balanced regional coverage, the 422 respondents **were distributed** proportionately across the five South-East states based on the number of eligible organizations identified in each state. Where a reliable proportional frame **was not available** at the early stage, equal allocation **was used** initially and later adjusted during field validation.

3.4 Sources of Data

The study **made use of primary data**. The primary data **were collected** directly from respondents through a structured questionnaire. Primary data **were appropriate** because the key variables in the study, such as bonding social capital, bridging social capital, linking social capital, production innovation, process innovation, institutional innovation, social value identification, social value appropriation, social value mechanism, social value dimension, scale, depth, duration, additionality, employment creation, and poverty alleviation, **were best measured** through responses from actors involved in social entrepreneurial activities.

3.55 Instrument for Data Collection

The questionnaire was developed in line with the objectives of the study, the study variables, and the specified empirical models.

3.6 Method of Data Analysis

The inferential analysis was carried out using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM). PLS-SEM was suitable for this study because the study involved multiple latent variables and several dimensions under the independent variable. It also estimated direct and moderating relationships. In addition, the study was prediction-oriented and framework-building in nature. The model contained reflective constructs that required measurement model and structural model assessment. PLS-SEM also performed well in complex models involving many indicators and relationships.

3.7 Model Specification

3.7.1 Model One: Social Capital and Poverty Alleviation

To achieve objective one, which examined the effect of bonding social capital, bridging social capital, and linking social capital on poverty

alleviation in South-East Nigeria, Model One was specified as:

$$PA_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BOSCi + \beta_2 BRSCi + \beta_3 LISCi + \mu_i$$

Where:

PA=Poverty Alleviation

BOSC=Bonding Social Capital

BRSC=Bridging Social Capital

LISC=Linking Social Capital

β_0 =Constant term

β_1 – β_3 =Parameter estimates

This model was linked to Shiaki et al. (2024), who examined the impact of social capital on poverty reduction in Benue State, Nigeria, using survey data and logit regression. Their findings showed that major dimensions of social participation significantly reduced poverty.

3.7.2 Model Two: Social Innovation and Poverty Alleviation

To achieve objective two, which determined the effect of production innovation, process innovation, and institutional innovation on poverty alleviation in South-East Nigeria, Model Two was specified as:

$$PA_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PRIN_i + \beta_2 PROC_i + \beta_3 INST_i + \mu_i$$

Where:

PA = Poverty Alleviation

PRIN = Production Innovation

PROC = Process Innovation

INST = Institutional Innovation

β_0 =Constant term

β_1 – β_3 =Parameter estimates

This model was linked to Fagbemi and Ajibike (2024), who examined whether process innovation affected poverty reduction in Nigeria from 2000 to 2021 and found a significant effect in both the short run and the long run. It was also linked to Nahuche et al. (2024), who found that social innovation had a significant positive relationship with poverty alleviation.

Table 4.1: Regression Results for Model One: Social Capital and Poverty Alleviation

3.7.3 Model Three: Social Value Creation and Poverty Alleviation

To achieve objective three, which assessed the effect of social value identification, social value appropriation, social value mechanism, and social value dimension on poverty alleviation in South-East Nigeria, Model Three was specified as:

$$PA_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SVID_i + \beta_2 SVAP_i + \beta_3 SVME_i + \beta_4 SVDI_i + \mu_i$$

Where:

PA = Poverty Alleviation

SVID=Social Value Identification

SVAP=Social Value Appropriation

SVME=Social Value Mechanism

SVDI=Social Value Dimension

β_0 =Constant term

β_1 – β_4 =Parameter estimates

This model was linked mainly to Arejiogbe et al. (2023) and Nahuche et al. (2024). Arejiogbe et al. found that social value had a positive relationship with poverty alleviation in Nigeria. Nahuche et al. also examined social value and poverty alleviation, although their result suggested contextual variation. The present study therefore extended the literature by disaggregating social value creation into clearer measurable dimensions.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Test of Hypotheses

The hypotheses of the study were tested at the 5 per cent level of significance in line with the decision rule stated in the methodology. Separate regression models were estimated for each specific objective. The results are presented in Tables 4.8 to 4.12.

4.1.1 Model One: Social Capital and Poverty Alleviation

Variable	B	Std. Error	t	p-value	Decision
Constant	2.453	0.168	14.620	0.000	Significant
BOSC_IDX	0.094	0.065	1.451	0.148	Not Sig.
BRSC_IDX	0.095	0.061	1.544	0.123	Not Sig.
LISC_IDX	0.158	0.062	2.564	0.011	Significant
Model Summary	$R^2 = 0.106$ Adjusted $R^2 = 0.100$ $F = 16.559$ $Prob(F) = 0.000$				

Source: Author’s computation from SPSS Output, 2026.

The result in Table 4.1 shows that the overall model was statistically significant because the probability value of the F-statistic was 0.000, which was less than 0.05. The adjusted R^2 value of 0.100 indicates that social capital dimensions jointly explained 10.0 per cent of the variation in poverty alleviation.

At the individual level, bonding social capital had a positive coefficient of 0.094, but the effect was not statistically significant at the 5 per cent level because the p-value was 0.148. Bridging social capital also had a positive coefficient of 0.095, but it was not statistically significant because the p-value was 0.123. Linking social

capital, however, had a positive coefficient of 0.158 and was statistically significant because the p-value was 0.011.

This means that among the dimensions of social capital, linking social capital was the strongest predictor of poverty alleviation in the Southeast Nigeria. The result suggests that ties with institutions, agencies, and formal support structures may matter more for poverty reduction outcomes than internal or horizontal ties alone. Since the overall model was significant, the null hypothesis was rejected. It was therefore concluded that social capital dimensions had significant effects on poverty alleviation.

4.2.2 Model Two: Social Innovation and Poverty Alleviation

Table 4.2: Regression Results for Model Two: Social Innovation and Poverty Alleviation

Variable	B	Std. Error	t	p-value	Decision
Constant	2.187	0.160	13.686	0.000	Significant
PRIN_IDX	0.074	0.060	1.241	0.215	Not Sig.
PROC_IDX	0.180	0.063	2.861	0.004	Significant
INST_IDX	0.178	0.064	2.793	0.005	Significant
Model Summary	$R^2 = 0.169$ Adjusted $R^2 = 0.163$ $F = 28.376$				

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	Prob(F) = 0.000.
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Source: Author’s computation from SPSS Output, 2026.

Table 4.2 shows that the overall model was statistically significant because the probability value of the F-statistic was 0.000. The adjusted R² value of 0.163 indicates that the social innovation dimensions jointly explained 16.3 per cent of the variation in poverty alleviation.

Production innovation had a positive coefficient of 0.074, but its p-value of 0.215 shows that the effect was not statistically significant. Process innovation had a coefficient of 0.180 and a p-value of 0.004. Institutional innovation had a coefficient of 0.178 and a p-value of 0.005. Both

variables had positive and statistically significant effects on poverty alleviation.

The implication is that the way social ventures organise, deliver, and institutionalise their activities mattered more than product-related novelty in the model. This suggests that process efficiency and supportive institutional arrangements may be central pathways through which social entrepreneurship contributes to poverty reduction. Since the overall model was significant, the null hypothesis was rejected. It was therefore concluded that social innovation dimensions had significant effects on poverty alleviation.

4.1.3 Model Three: Social Value Creation and Poverty Alleviation

Table 4.3: Regression Results for Model Three: Social Value Creation and Poverty Alleviation

Variable	B	Std. Error	t	p-value	Decision
Constant	2.233	0.173	12.905	0.000	Significant
SVID_IDX	0.185	0.063	2.942	0.003	Significant
SVAP_IDX	0.141	0.063	2.223	0.027	Significant
SVME_IDX	0.064	0.065	0.989	0.323	Not Sig.
SVDI_IDX	0.012	0.065	0.186	0.852	Not Sig.
Model Summary	R ² = 0.140 Adjusted R ² = 0.132 F = 17.027 Prob(F) = 0.000.				

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Source: Author's computation from SPSS Output, 2026.

The result in Table 4.1.3 indicates that the overall model was statistically significant because the F-statistic probability value was 0.000. The adjusted R^2 of 0.132 means that the social value creation dimensions explained 13.2 per cent of the variation in poverty alleviation.

Social value identification had a positive coefficient of 0.185 and was statistically significant at $p = 0.003$. Social value appropriation had a positive coefficient of 0.141 and was also significant at $p = 0.027$. Social value mechanism and social value dimension had positive coefficients of 0.064 and 0.012 respectively, but their p-values of 0.323 and 0.852 show that they were not statistically significant.

This result means that the ability to identify real community needs and retain benefits for social good had stronger explanatory power for poverty alleviation than the other social value creation dimensions. The result supports the view that value creation becomes more relevant to poverty reduction when it is tied closely to real social problems and when the resulting benefits are directed toward social welfare. Since the overall model was significant, the null hypothesis was rejected. It was therefore concluded that social value creation dimensions had significant effects on poverty alleviation.

CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The study concluded that poverty alleviation in South-East Nigeria is more likely to improve where social ventures maintain strong institutional and external linkages, adopt effective process and institutional innovations, identify real community needs, direct created value toward social welfare, and generate social

impact that is broad in reach, sustained over time, and attributable to the intervention. These dimensions emerged as the most important channels through which social entrepreneurship influenced poverty alleviation in the study area. The study also concluded that linking social capital was more important than bonding social capital and bridging social capital in explaining poverty alleviation. This implies that the poverty reduction value of social entrepreneurship depends more on the extent to which social ventures are connected to formal institutions and external support structures than on internal and peer-level ties alone. In the same way, process innovation and institutional innovation were more important than production innovation. This shows that poverty alleviation depends more on how social entrepreneurial activities are organized, coordinated, and delivered than on product novelty alone.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made.

First, social ventures, cooperatives, community-based organizations, women empowerment groups, youth development groups, and other grassroots initiatives in South-East Nigeria should strengthen their institutional and external linkages with government agencies, donor bodies, financial institutions, and development partners. This is necessary because linking social capital was the only social capital dimension that significantly improved poverty alleviation.

Second, managers and coordinators of social ventures should give greater attention to process innovation and institutional innovation. This means that emphasis should be placed on better programme delivery, stronger coordination systems, improved administrative

arrangements, effective monitoring, and sustainable partnership structures.

Third, social entrepreneurship programmes should be based on proper identification of real community needs. Needs assessment should be

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